

POLARIN

POLAR
RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURE
NETWORK

Deliverable 4.5 Use case documents for data discovery processes

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SUMMARY

POLARIN's overarching goal is to provide efficient, tailored Research Infrastructure (RI) services that address the scientific challenges of the polar regions. This includes offering access to a broad portfolio of complementary and interdisciplinary, high-level RIs. By integrating the capabilities of polar RIs, POLARIN facilitates scientific research aimed at understanding and predicting key processes in polar regions within the context of climate change. This effort enhances society's ability to solve problems and supports evidence-based policymaking.

One of POLARIN's four core services is to improve access to data and develop online services and data products. This activity is coordinated by POLARIN's Work Package 4 (WP4). The present deliverable focuses on implementing this service through a front-end data portal designed to help users discover polar data tailored to their specific needs.

1. Introduction

The polar regions are at the forefront of global climate change, serving both as early warning systems and as complex laboratories for understanding Earth system dynamics. In recent decades, these remote environments have become the focus of increasingly collaborative and interdisciplinary scientific efforts. This evolution has fostered a dynamic, interconnected polar data ecosystem shaped by international partnerships, robust infrastructures, and a growing commitment to open science.

Initiatives such as the Polar Data Forum (PDF), the Polar Observing Assets Working Group (POAwg), and legacy efforts like the Arctic Data Committee (ADC) and the International Polar Year (IPY) have laid a strong foundation for data sharing, ecosystem mapping, and long-term observing strategies. More recent frameworks, including the Arctic Observing Summit (AOS), Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) and the Registry of Polar Observing Networks (RoPON), continue to advance community-driven solutions, with a focus on semantic interoperability, metadata harmonization and the long-term sustainability of observing systems.

Despite this progress, the polar data landscape remains fragmented. Data are collected by a wide range of stakeholders, such as research institutions, national polar programs, NGOs and private entities, often using different standards, vocabularies, and access protocols. This heterogeneity limits the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of data, making it difficult for users to identify and access datasets that best meet their scientific, operational or policy-driven needs.

POLARIN represents a significant step forward in coordinating polar research infrastructure. With a network of 61 Arctic and Antarctic Research Infrastructures, including research stations, vessels, observatories, data infrastructures, and core repositories, POLARIN provides both transnational and virtual access to essential resources for understanding polar processes. These include long-term datasets and in situ observations.

The project focuses on regions particularly vulnerable to climate change, with an emphasis on one or more of the following research topics:

- sea ice and polar oceans;
- sea level, glacier stability, and melt;
- carbon balance and permafrost;
- polar ecosystems and biodiversity;

-
- atmospheric dynamics;
 - (paleo)climate processes.

In terms of data preservation, POLARIN is developing a system to ensure that metadata and data are hosted long-term in trusted national repositories. When appropriate, copies of data will also be shared with key European and international initiatives aligned with POLARIN's data goals.

To address the challenges of data fragmentation and usability, Work Package 4 (WP4) of the POLARIN project focuses on improving both data accessibility and consumption. Through technical harmonization, semantic interoperability and user-oriented service design, WP4 aims to enable seamless data integration across infrastructures and disciplines. Central to this effort is the POLARIN Data Portal (DP): a unified platform that brings together diverse polar data assets through a standards-compliant interface. By integrating data from multiple repositories and aligning with international best practices, the Data Portal supports a broad spectrum of stakeholders, from researchers and educators to policymakers and environmental managers.

This report explores the usability aspects of the POLARIN Data Portal and related services, identifying key stakeholder categories, analysing user needs, and outlining goals for enhancing the user experience. As the polar research community continues to evolve, POLARIN aims not only to provide access to data, but to ensure these data are meaningful, actionable, and usable across a wide range of scientific and societal contexts.

2. Identification of target users

2.1. Known project users

POLARIN is built around a unique constellation of stakeholders deeply engaged in the exploration, monitoring, and sustainable stewardship of the polar regions. Given the vast and interdisciplinary nature of polar science, the project draws upon and serves a wide spectrum of actors, ranging from scientists and infrastructure providers to policy makers and private entities.

Research Infrastructures and polar scientists

At the heart of POLARIN's stakeholder ecosystem are the research institutions that operate and utilize the 61 polar Research Infrastructures (RIs) integrated into the network. These institutions are responsible for field stations in the Arctic and Antarctic, icebreakers, research vessels and a growing number of observatories and long-term monitoring sites. They also include leading universities, national polar programs and international collaborations (e.g., INTERACT, ARICE). These actors are the primary users of POLARIN's Transnational Access (TA) and Virtual Access (VA) services and represent a community with advanced needs: access to remote locations, complex datasets, cross-disciplinary collaboration and infrastructure-sharing mechanisms.

Environmental and climate monitoring agencies

POLARIN contributes to global efforts to track and understand climate change. Agencies responsible for climate and environmental monitoring, both at the national, European and international levels, are key stakeholders. These actors rely on harmonized, interoperable datasets for tracking critical parameters such as sea ice extent, permafrost thawing, atmospheric composition and biodiversity. Virtual access tools and aggregated data products developed under POLARIN directly support this group's mandate to monitor environmental trends and inform mitigation strategies.

Policy makers and decision-makers

Given the polar regions' sensitivity to climate change and their geopolitical relevance, there is a growing need to translate scientific outputs into policy-relevant insights. Policy makers, environmental ministries and Arctic/Antarctic governance bodies are indirect users of the infrastructure but crucial stakeholders in the use of POLARIN's outputs (e.g., particularly synthesized datasets, maps and evidence that can guide regulation and international cooperation). For this group, accessibility, clarity, and reliability of information are critical usability factors.

Data repositories and interoperability platforms

POLARIN also interfaces with a range of data infrastructures responsible for long-term data curation, archiving and dissemination. Examples include PANGAEA, EMODnet Physics, Copernicus Service and GOOS. These stakeholders ensure that data collected are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR). They also support secondary users who access the data beyond the original research context.

Education and capacity building stakeholders

POLARIN emphasizes the training of the next generation of polar researchers as a strategic goal. Educational institutions, graduate schools, early-career research networks (e.g., APECS) and training programs are thus direct stakeholders in usability design. These users need clear, well-documented access protocols and training materials, including interfaces that support learning by doing (e.g., simplified tools, sample data sets, guided analysis workflows).

Private sector actors

A distinctive feature of POLARIN is its collaboration with private infrastructure operators such as the Tara Ocean Foundation and the cruise company Ponant. These stakeholders not only contribute physical access units (e.g., via vessels) but also represent a category of users with a strong logistical, technological, or exploration-driven interest in the polar regions. Involvement of the private sector introduces different usability expectations: emphasis on operational efficiency, robust data exchange mechanisms and possibly service-oriented interfaces.

Civil society and public engagement

Finally, while not primary users of complex datasets or infrastructure access, the general public and broader civil society are important end-beneficiaries of the knowledge produced through POLARIN. The project commits to open science, public outreach and the sharing of research results in accessible formats, helping to build awareness of polar challenges and foster societal engagement with science. For this audience, usability means accessibility of narratives, visualizations, and high-level summaries, rather than raw data.

2.1.1. User Types / Personas

While stakeholders vary in institutional roles and mandates, their interaction with the POLARIN ecosystem, especially the data infrastructure, can be further clarified through **three main user personas**, based on their levels of technical expertise, data needs, and use contexts:

1. advance users (Table 1);
 2. intermediate users (Table 2);
- non-expert or indirect users (

3. Table 3).

Table 1. Advance users' profile.

Advance users	
Description	These users are primarily found among the RI operating polar infrastructure and among the data repositories and interoperability platforms ensuring FAIR access. They engage with POLARIN both as data producers and power users of Transnational and Virtual Access services.
Who they are	Polar scientists, data managers, infrastructure operators
Typical needs	Access to complex datasets; support for scripting environments (Python, MATLAB, R); full metadata transparency; interoperability with existing repositories
Portal implications	Need for detailed filtering, advanced search, and direct download options in standardized formats

Table 2. Intermediate users' profile

Intermediate users	
Description	This persona is particularly relevant to educational institutions and capacity building stakeholders such as APECS and university programs. These users are often transitioning into more advanced roles and thus need tools that can evolve with their expertise.
Who they are	PhD students, early-career researchers, trainees in polar science
Typical needs	Guided workflows; simplified tools for analysis; well-documented datasets; examples and tutorials
Portal implications	Require user-friendly interfaces that still offer scientific depth, plus support for learning-by-doing

Table 3. Non-expert or indirect users

Non-expert or indirect users	
Description	This persona cuts across policy and decision-makers, civil society and public engagement, and even parts of the private sector, especially those not involved in scientific research but interested in outcomes and trends.
Who they are	Policy makers, educators, civil society, NGOs, the general public
Typical needs	Synthesis-level information; visualizations; clarity and accessibility; impact summaries
Portal implications	Require simplified navigation, dashboards, and storytelling approaches over raw data access

By recognizing that many stakeholders fall into one or more of these user types, POLARIN can align its usability and data access strategies with the varied expectations of its ecosystem. In practical terms, this means the data portal and virtual services must strike a balance between technical depth and user-friendliness, delivering both robust tools for scientists and digestible, actionable insights for broader audiences.

2.2. Needs analysis through questionnaires

To ensure the POLARIN Data Portal responds effectively to the needs of its user community, a needs assessment was carried out through targeted surveys. These surveys were designed to collect both qualitative and quantitative insights on data discovery habits, user preferences and expectations around data portals.

2.2.1. Methodology used for the survey

The questionnaires conducted as part of the need analysis targeted a diverse but well-defined audience that reflects the key user personas and stakeholder groups identified in POLARIN. The questionnaire campaign adopted a mixed approach, combining internal and external engagements.

Internal Survey – WP4 Extended Meeting (24 February 2025)

The first set of responses was gathered during an internal meeting of Work Package 4 (WP4), which focuses on improving data accessibility and interoperability within POLARIN. The internal survey was completed by participants directly involved in the POLARIN project, including researchers, data managers and infrastructure operators. These are typically **advanced users** with experience in data collection, portal design and interoperability challenges across the polar research ecosystem.

The question asked were:

- *When you work or browse for polar data, what is the first feature you look for in a data portal?*
- *When you need to access polar data, which portal or service comes to mind first?*

Extended Survey – Public Webinars and External Events

Recognizing the importance of capturing feedback from a broader audience, the same or similar questions were extended to participants in webinars and conferences not directly linked to POLARIN. These sessions aimed to explore how secondary users (i.e., those not directly affiliated with the project but who may still benefit from its services) interact with data portals.

A total of three stakeholder events were conducted, engaging a range of 61 participants with diverse backgrounds in data science, oceanography, polar research, and geospatial analysis. Respondents included data analysts, scientific researchers, decision makers, students and educators, many of whom are active in related domains such as marine and atmospheric science, environmental monitoring and geospatial data services. These participants align with the **intermediate** and **non-expert user personas**, offering insights into needs and usability expectations from a wider scientific and operational community.

The refined set of questions included:

- *When you need in situ data, which portal or service comes to mind first?*
- *When you work with or browse for in situ data, what is the first feature you look for in a data portal?*
- *Which of these tools do you feel most confident using? Which one would you prefer to use first when interacting with data?*

2.2.2. Summary of main findings

Internal Survey (WP4 Extended Meeting)

When you work or browse for polar data, what is the first feature you look for in a data portal?

The results of the survey are shown in Figure 1. The most prominent word was *variable*, indicating that users most often seek information about what variables are available (e.g., temperature, salinity, wind speed) before anything else. This aligns with the fundamental need to ensure the dataset includes parameters relevant to their research or analysis.

Closely following are terms like *data*, *easy*, *parameter* and *coverage/time*. These suggest that users also value ease of use, quick access to key parameters, and clear temporal and spatial coverage. The emphasis on *easy interface* and *available* reinforces the importance of user-friendly design and accessible data.

Smaller but still notable entries like *look for a map*, *site/platform*, *specific site* and *data coverage* indicate that users appreciate tools for spatial exploration and geographic filtering, as well as clear metadata that helps determine whether the dataset fits their study region and timeframe.

Overall, the word cloud paints a picture of users looking for:

- relevant content (variables, parameters);
- usability (easy interface, searchability);
- coverage (spatial and temporal).

When you work with or browse for polar data, what is the first feature you look for in a data portal?

Figure 1. Internal survey, first question results.

When you need to access polar data, which portal or service comes to mind first?

As shown in Figure 2, national data centers stand out as the most commonly mentioned resource, accounting for 24% of the responses. This suggests that researchers often rely on their own country’s infrastructures, likely due to familiarity, trust in data quality, or access convenience. Close behind are responses mentioning SIOS (Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System), which was selected by 19% of participants. This indicates its importance and visibility, especially in Arctic observational efforts.

Zenodo and PANGAEA were mentioned by 14% of respondents, reflecting the growing role of open-access repositories that host interdisciplinary datasets. These platforms appear to serve as reliable alternatives, particularly when institutional or specialized data centers aren’t available.

The Arctic Data Center received 10% of mentions, reaffirming that regionally focused data infrastructures are recognized, though perhaps not as widely known as larger platforms.

Interestingly, 10% of respondents answered with “depends”, signaling variability in platform choice depending on the specific data needs, research context, or region of interest.

Several platforms (i.e., SOOS, INTERACT, ACTRIS, EBAS, and Copernicus) each received a single mention, representing 5% each. These may serve more specialized roles, be tied to specific projects, or reflect niche areas of research.

Altogether, the data suggest that while there’s no single dominant portal for accessing polar data, national infrastructures, well-known regional systems like SIOS, and open repositories such as Zenodo and PANGAEA form the backbone of most researchers’ data access strategies.

Figure 2. Internal survey, frequency percentages of preferred portal and services.

Extended Survey – Public Webinars and External Events

When you need in situ data, which portal or service comes to mind first?

Figure 3 reflects user preferences or behaviors regarding data sources, highlighting a strong reliance on Copernicus, which includes CMEMS (Copernicus Marine Environmental Service), mentioned by 40% of respondents. This dominant share indicates Copernicus' central role as a trusted, go-to platform for polar or environmental data.

The "Others" category, accounting for 20%, suggests a long tail of individually mentioned sources, pointing to a diverse ecosystem of specialized or niche platforms that may be important for specific needs or communities.

Google (12%) and EMODnet (11%) follow as significant secondary sources. Google's popularity may reflect its ease of access and familiarity as well as generic research, while EMODnet's presence underscores the importance of marine data infrastructures.

Mentions of PANGAEA (6%) show recognition of established scientific data repositories, particularly for geoscience and environmental research.

A smaller portion of users (5%) rely on institutional or personal cloud storage solutions, indicating a degree of data decentralization and possibly limited discoverability or standardization.

Geoportals (3%) and non-valid answers (3%) comprise the smallest segments, suggesting either limited usage of structured geoportals or some confusion/lack of clarity among users.

Figure 3. External survey, frequency percentages of preferred portal and services.

When you work with or browse for in situ data, what is the first feature you look for in a data portal?

For sake of clarity, the answers obtained from the first question have been categorized into the groups displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. Categories for data portal features.

Category	Sample keywords / phrases
Data access & download	Direct download, easy access, download, open data, clarity, easy extraction, connectivity
Metadata & quality	Quality, value and uncertainty, standardized metadata, clear description, accuracy, data details
Search & usability	Search, search bar, user friendly, interface, rapid access, clear interface
Temporal & spatial info	Temporal coverage, time scale, spatial resolution, coordinates, time span, frequency, time and space info
Variables & parameters	Variable, ocean levels, parameters, temperature, geographical area, available variables
Visualization & interface	Map selection, data viewer, visual tools, dashboards, graphics, visual interface

<p>Data Structure & formats</p>	<p>Tidy data, aggregation, multiplatform, export analysis results, database filters</p>
<p>Navigation & Filtering</p>	<p>Filters, menu with pions, easy browsing, search filtering</p>

For each of the categories, Figure 4 shows the percentage distribution. Data access & download was the most mentioned category (23%). Users want quick, direct access to data, ideally via downloadable files or open data portals. Keywords like *easy access*, *open data* and *direct download* show that accessibility and data retrieval are top of mind.

Users also highly value user-friendly interfaces, search functions, and general ease of navigation (Search & usability, 18%). Repeated mentions of *search bar*, *easy and clear access* and *user friendly* suggest users get frustrated when they can't find what they're looking for quickly.

Details like time coverage, spatial resolution, and temporal frequency were frequently requested (Temporal & spatial info, 16%). Users need to know if the data covers the area and time period relevant to their work.

In addition to access and usability, users placed notable emphasis on the quality and clarity of metadata, with 14.8% of responses highlighting the importance of well-documented, trustworthy data. This underscores a strong desire for transparency and clear standards that help users understand and evaluate datasets effectively.

A smaller, yet significant, portion of users (9.8%) focused on the availability of specific variables and parameters, such as temperature or salinity, which are essential for assessing the relevance of a dataset right from the start.

Visualization and interface design, while not the primary concern, still accounted for 8.2% of the responses. Users appreciate having visual tools, dashboards, and interactive elements that allow them to explore the data before committing to a download.

About 6.6% of participants emphasized the value of tidy, well-structured datasets. This reflects a practical concern: clean formats are much easier to analyze and integrate into workflows, especially for research or reporting.

Finally, a smaller group (3.2%) noted the usefulness of navigation aids and filtering options. While less frequently mentioned, this feedback suggests that there's room to enhance how users browse, search, and refine their data discovery process.

Figure 4. External survey, frequency percentages of preferred features in data portals.

Which of these tools do you feel most confident using? Which one would you prefer to use first when interacting with data?

As shown in Figure 5, the data shows a balanced preference between Python and spreadsheets (Excel, Google Sheets, etc.), each used by 33% of respondents. This indicates two dominant user profiles: those using script-based analytical tools and those relying on more familiar, GUI-driven platforms for data exploration and processing.

Matlab ranks next with 18%. Meanwhile, R accounts for 10%, reflecting its niche but important role in statistical computing and data visualization.

Less commonly used platforms include GeoServer (5%) and ERDDAP (2%), which are more specialized tools geared towards geospatial data management and server-based data access, respectively. Their lower adoption may reflect their complexity or the specific expertise required to use them effectively.

Figure 5. External survey, frequency percentages of preferred tool for analyzing data.

2.3. Research topics interests of RIs

In addition to collecting user feedback via surveys, the POLARIN team assessed the research topics focus of its participating RIs to better align portal development with scientific priorities. Out of the 61 RI, 55 indicated which of the six core research themes they are actively involved in. The results (Figure 6) show a strong concentration of interest in (Paleo)climate processes (52 RIs, 95%) and Polar ecosystems and biodiversity and Atmosphere dynamics (each with 50 RIs, 91%). These areas are followed by Sea level, glacier stability and melt (38 RIs, 69%) and Sea-ice and Polar Oceans (36 RIs, 65%), while Carbon balance and permafrost is still significant but with comparatively less engagement (24 RIs, 44%).

Figure 6. Percentage of RIs dealing with the research topics.

This distribution provides a strategic lens for data portal design: datasets and discovery tools related to high-interest themes should be prominently featured, with semantic and spatial filters aligned to those domains. Furthermore, the lower, but still substantial, engagement in themes like permafrost and carbon balance signals a need for improving visibility and discoverability in those areas, potentially encouraging future integration efforts.

Beyond the individual topics, an important insight emerges from analyzing how many of them each RI is interested in (Table 5). As the table shows, only 4 out of 55 RIs are focused on a single topic, and all of these are engaged specifically with (Paleo)climate processes. Conversely, 11 RIs engage with all six research topic areas, and the majority—over 65%—are interested in at least five themes. This highlights the strong multidisciplinary nature of the polar research community.

Table 5. Number of RIs expressing interest in one or more research topics.

Number of themes of interest	Number of RIs	Notes
1	4	All focused on (Paleo)climate (Theme 6)
2	0	—
3	6	Mostly interested in Themes 4–6; one in Themes 2, 5, 6
4	8	Varies

These patterns underscore the need for a flexible and interconnected data portal design. Rather than separating information strictly by research topic, the portal should enable users to explore datasets across thematic boundaries, combining variables and filters from multiple scientific domains. Tools such as multi-theme search, linked visualizations and interoperable metadata will be essential to support the broad research agendas represented by most RIs.

3. Functional needs and expectations

The polar data landscape is shaped by decades of collaborative efforts across institutions, nations, and disciplines. As outlined in the introduction, this ecosystem, while rich in information, faces persistent challenges related to fragmentation, accessibility and interoperability. The goal of WP4 within the POLARIN project has been to address these challenges by developing tools and solutions that make data more usable, findable, and harmonized across systems and communities. This chapter synthesizes the key insights that emerged from the internal stakeholder surveys and interactive events conducted during the WP4 extended meeting and partner workshops.

3.1. Key needs across user personas

The survey responses and subsequent discussions revealed that despite different levels of expertise, different user personas share some overlapping priorities when it comes to accessing data. A key theme across all stakeholder groups is the need for intuitive, user-friendly interfaces. Regardless of technical background, participants consistently emphasized the importance of portals that are easy to navigate and where key functions such as data download, filtering and variable browsing are immediately visible and understandable.

Another frequently expressed priority is the ability to efficiently search and filter data based on key dimensions. Users highlighted the value of being able to search by variable name or parameter, filter by specific time periods and geographic regions, and navigate datasets through both text-based and map-based interfaces. This reflects a clear demand for platforms that support both exploratory browsing and precise, targeted queries.

Transparency of data availability also emerged as a critical issue. Users expect clear indicators of what parameters are measured, where the data were collected and over what time periods. Such transparency is essential for assessing the relevance, completeness and comparability of data sets.

Direct data download and interoperability with widely used analysis tools were also identified as key needs. Users want data to be easily downloadable in standard, analysis-ready formats that integrate

smoothly with tools such as Python, MATLAB, R and Excel. This expectation is closely linked to the FAIR principles, which emphasize the importance of accessible and reusable data.

Finally, the importance of high-quality metadata was a recurring theme. Standardized metadata are essential to make data truly usable. This includes clear documentation of collection methods, spatial and temporal resolution, uncertainty or quality indicators, and coordinate or reference systems. These elements are seen as fundamental to accurately interpreting data and ensuring that it can be integrated into wider analyses.

3.2. Identified priorities for portal design

Drawing from these shared and persona-specific needs, several design priorities have emerged for the development of the POLARIN Data Portal:

- unified access to data across disciplines, regions and catalogues;
- intuitive map-based and variable-based search functionality;
- improved visibility of data availability and coverage;
- support for standard download formats and workflows;
- high-quality metadata structured around FAIR principles;
- adaptability to different technical levels and user types;

These findings provide the foundation upon which the POLARIN Data Portal has been designed. The next chapter presents the portal's structure, key functionalities and how it aims to meet these cross-cutting and stakeholder-specific needs.

4. POLARIN Data Hub

The main objective of the POLARIN Data Hub (DH) is to provide a single, intuitive access point for discovering and accessing the growing, heterogeneous collections of polar data and data products, including satellite, airborne (drones, aircraft) and in-situ sensor observations from both the Arctic and Antarctic.

In line with project ambitions and stakeholder needs, the POLARIN DH is envisioned as:

“A hub where experts as well as intermediaries and non-experts are guided to find data and information necessary to match their specific needs, and where tailored tools and services support both discovery and use.”

More technical information about POLARIN Data Hub is outlined in Deliverable D4.3 Web Portal.

4.1. Data Portal design and navigation

A preliminary version of the POLARIN Data Portal is live at <https://s4polarin.eu>.

4.1.1. Landing Page

The landing page (Figure 7) is designed for intuitive interaction, guiding users through multiple data dimensions. The interface is organized around usability. It informs users about the volume, coverage,

and access conditions of available datasets. Pre-defined filters, based on POLARIN’s scientific challenges, streamline exploration. A top navigation bar links to core tools: Data Viewer, Data Catalogue, POLARIN Zenodo Community and Cookbook repositories¹.

The main components of the landing page are:

- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which show how many datasets and variables are currently available;
- Stations map, where the user can visualize the geographic location of participating RIs in both polar regions;
- Data Integration Panels, which will include use cases (notebooks) elaborates from POLARIN data.

In the right-hand Panels the user can explore:

- Data exploration menu, where it is possible to filter by RI, climate system sphere or research topics;
- Networks section, which display the direct links to external resources (e.g., RoPON, FACE-IT, Core Repositories).

Figure 7. POLARIN DH Landing Page

4.1.2. Data Catalog

¹ <https://github.com/he-polarin>

The POLARIN Data Catalog (<https://s4polarin.eu/data-catalog/>, Figure 8) functions like a shopping basket. Users can view essential metadata for each dataset, add items to a personal “basket” for later download or exploration and access a dynamic feed of records coming from POLARIN’s connected data nodes.

This design prioritizes clarity and efficiency, ensuring users know what’s available and how to get it.

Figure 8. POLARIN DH Catalog

4.1.3. Data Viewer

The POLARIN Data Viewer (<https://s4polarin.eu/data-viewer/>, Figure 9) offers deeper interactive access to datasets selected via the catalogue. Within the viewer:

- A control panel allows filtering by RI, parameter, time range, etc.
- A free-text search bar improves discoverability
- The main display shows datasets in space, with interactive navigation through time and depth

For each dataset, a popup (when applicable) shows summary information, a link to dynamic data plots or graphs and a direct link to the full dataset.

This system enables users to not only discover and visualize data but also to interact with it meaningfully.

Figure 9. POLARIN DH Data Viewer

5. Representative use cases

5.1. Use Case 1: advanced analysis of water column properties

Persona: Advanced user, oceanographer or biogeochemist.

Goal: to retrieve and analyze multi-depth oceanographic data (temperature, salinity, nutrients, oxygen) from specific polar regions to understand gradients and fluxes and their seasonal variability.

Workflow Steps:

1. Access the Data Catalog (Figure 10):

- navigate to the POLARIN Data Portal's homepage;
- click on the "Data Catalog" link to enter the catalogue interface.

Figure 10. Access the Data Catalog.

2. Filter datasets by relevant variables (Figure 11):

- in the Data Catalog, use the filtering options to select datasets containing variables such as temperature, salinity, oxygen, chlorophyll, and nutrients;
- apply additional filters for example for specific regions (Arctic or Antarctic) and timeframes to narrow down the datasets to those most pertinent to your study.

Figure 11. Filter by variable.

3. Preview datasets in the map viewer (Figure 12, Figure 13):

- after identifying relevant datasets, utilize the Data Viewer to visualize the data (e.g., use temporal navigation tools to observe data across different seasons or years, generate plots to analyze gradients)

Figure 12. Utilize the Data Viewer to explore the data.

Figure 13. Visualize the related graph.

4. **Export data for custom analysis (Figure 14):**

- download the selected datasets in compatible formats;
- import the data into analytical tools such as MATLAB, Python, or R for advanced processing, modeling, and integration into ecosystem or circulation models.

Figure 14. Download the dataset.

5.2. Use Case 2: student research —where is there insufficient data?

Persona: PhD student / graduate class.

Goal: investigate data availability across Arctic or Antarctic regions to identify gaps and propose new areas of research.

Workflow Steps:

1. **Explore landing page KPIs (Figure 15):**

- visit the POLARIN Data Portal's landing page;
- review the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to understand the volume and distribution of datasets available.

Figure 15. Review the KPIs in the landing page.

2. Analyze dataset distribution (Figure 16):

- access the Data Catalog to assess the number of datasets available per Research Topic or Climate System Sphere;
- utilize filtering options to identify underrepresented regions, variables, or time periods.

Figure 16. Access the Data Catalog per Climate System Sphere or Research Topic.

3. Identify data gaps:

- compare the spatial and temporal distribution of datasets to known areas of scientific interest;
- document regions or topics with sparse data coverage that could benefit from further investigation.

5.3. Use Case 3: Exploring temperature trends at Arctic stations

Persona: Policy analyst or decision maker

Goal: Understand long-term temperature changes at selected Arctic sites to inform policy decisions.

Workflow Steps:

1. Filter datasets by temperature (Figure 17):

- navigate to the Data Catalogue from the POLARIN homepage;
- apply filters to select datasets containing variables such as "temperature" or "air temperature";
- further refine the search by specifying the Arctic region and relevant timeframes.

Figure 17. Filter the Data Catalog by variable.

2. Visualize data in the Data Viewer (Figure 18):

- click on individual stations to access detailed plots of temperature variations over time;
- utilize temporal navigation tools to observe trends across different periods.

Figure 18. Visualize the data in the Data Viewer.

3. Export data and visualizations (Figure 19):

- download graphs and underlying data for inclusion in reports or presentations;
- incorporate findings into policy briefings to support evidence-based decision-making regarding climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Figure 19. Download the graphs.

6. Conclusion

This document has outlined the foundational user needs, stakeholder expectations and technical strategies that shape the development of the POLARIN Data Hub. Through questionnaire analysis, user persona mapping and exploration of current practices, several key findings emerged. Most users, from expert scientists to early-career researchers and decision-makers, seek accessible, well-documented, and interoperable data portals, with high demand for features such as map-based searches, metadata clarity, and compatibility with common analysis tools. The POLARIN Data Hub directly responds to these expectations by offering a clean, modular platform that integrates a dynamic catalogue, interactive viewer and links to core resources. The preliminary version already addresses usability across experience levels and provides guided exploration of climate-relevant polar data.

These insights will have a strong impact on the design of future services: usability must continue to be matched with interoperability, transparency, and data richness. Feedback loops with stakeholders, especially via interface testing and guided use cases, will be essential.

The development of the POLARIN Data Hub will continue to evolve through a series of targeted enhancements. A key priority will be the implementation of more granular filtering levels, particularly those allowing users to sort and access data by individual Research Infrastructures. In parallel, efforts will focus on introducing new layers of data and metadata aggregation, improving both discoverability and interpretability across scientific domains. To support advanced users and promote real-world applications of the portal, a series of use cases will be developed and disseminated through interactive notebooks, providing concrete, reproducible examples of data exploration and analysis.

These technical developments will be supported by iterative user testing cycles, ensuring that portal functionalities and interface design align with user needs and expectations. Continued backend integration will further enhance the depth and interoperability of available datasets, while dedicated training materials and workflow guidance will be tailored to serve a diverse audience, from early-career researchers to policy professionals. Collectively, these actions will help solidify POLARIN's role as a central, user-oriented gateway to polar research data.